

Studies on Synthesis and Antitubercular Activity of Some (+)- α -Aceto-*N,N'*-diarylsuccinamide

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($\pm$)- α -Aceto-*N,N'*-diaryl succinamide have been prepared and tested against $H_{37}R_v$ strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

BESIDES being a well-known local anaesthetic, ethyl 4-aminobenzoate (benzocaine) is also reported as antitubercular, fungicidal and antibacterial agent¹⁻⁵. The present communication is intended to report synthesis and antitubercular activity of *N*-substituted benzocaine derivatives and related compounds.

The reaction sequence has been presented in Scheme 1.

1 R=4-Carboethoxyphenyl; R'=Different aromatic moiety.

2 R=1-Naphthyl; R'=Different aromatic moiety.

Scheme 1

Experimental

Melting points of the compounds were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. The infrared spectra were recorded in KBr phase using a Backmann IR-20 spectrophotometer. The structure of the compounds have been established on the basis of their elemental analyses and ir spectrum. The ir spectra of the title compounds (1 and 2) show characteristic absorption at 1750-1760 (C=O) and 1705-1690 cm^{-1} (CONH).

Preparation of N-chloroacetylarylamine: Arylamine (15 g) was taken in benzene (75 ml) and chloroacetyl chloride (15 ml) in benzene (75 ml) was added to it. The contents were refluxed on water-bath for 2-3 h, cooled and the solvent was evaporated to get crystalline colourless product. It was washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution (4 M) and water to remove chloroacetyl chloride,

filtered, dried and recrystallised from benzene as colourless needles.

Preparation of acetoacet-p-carboethoxyanilide/acetoacet- α -naphthylide: To the solution of ethyl acetoacetate (0.12 M) in *p*-xylene (100 ml) was added very slowly ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate/ α -naphthylamine (0.1 M) at 135°, and the contents refluxed for 3.5 h, cooled, filtered and recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1).

Preparation of 2-aceto-*N,N'*-diarylsuccinamides: Acetoacetyl chloride (0.005 mol) and sodium (0.005 mol) separately dissolved in ethanol (25 ml; 99.5%) were mixed and refluxed for 10 min. To it was added appropriate chloroacetyl amine (0.005 mol) and the contents refluxed for 3 h, cooled, poured over ice, acidified with 0.1 M HCl, filtered, dried and recrystallised from 95% ethanol.

The physical and biological data have been presented in Tables 1 and 2

Biological screening: The *in vitro* antimicrobial activity of the compounds synthesised was studied at 5 and 30 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration using DMF as solvent against $H_{37}R_v$ strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* utilising Lowenstein-Jensen's egg medium (4 ml). The retardation of growth rate was

TABLE 1—DATA OF TITLE COMPOUND 1*

Sl. no.	R'	M.p. °C	Yield %	Antitubercular activity**	
				5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	80 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$
1.	C_6H_5	256	71	+	-
2.	2-Cl- C_6H_4	262	71	+	+
3.	3-Cl- C_6H_4	202	70	+	+
4.	4-Cl- C_6H_4	296	74	+	-
5.	4-OCH ₃ - C_6H_4	320	68	+	-
6.	3-OH ₂ - C_6H_4	316	68	+	-
7.	4-OH ₂ - C_6H_4	322	72	+	-
8.	1- C_{10}H_7	222	76	+	-
9.	4-OC ₂ H ₅ - C_6H_4	283	65	+	-
10.	4-OCOC ₂ H ₅ - C_6H_4	275	73	+	-

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N analysis.

** (+)=Inactive (no inhibition), (-)=Active.

TABLE 2—DATA OF TITLE COMPOUND 2*

Sl. no.	R'	M.p. °C	Yield %	Antitubercular activity**	
				µg ml ⁻¹	
				5	80
1.	C ₆ H ₅	289	61	+	-
2.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	218	63	+	+
3.	3-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	160	63	+	+
4.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	259	68	+	-
5.	3-OH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	208	60	+	-
6.	4-OH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	157	62	+	-
7.	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	126	58	+	-
8.	4-OC ₂ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄	179	52	+	-
9.	4-COOC ₂ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄	145	59	+	-
10.	1-C ₁₀ H ₇	218	64	+	-

* Explanation as in Table 1. ** Explanation as in Table 1.

studied upto six weeks at 37°. The procedure was duplicated using only solvent for control purposes. The screening results (Tables 1 and 2) show that

sixteen compounds are active at 30 µg ml⁻¹ concentration of the test substance, and 2-chlorophenyl and 3-chlorophenyl analogous are inactive.

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